

Research Article (DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.2014.6.0523014244>)

Hybrid Coffee (*Coffea arabica* L) Genotypes Quality Evaluation under different Environment of Southern Ethiopia

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ARTICLE INFO

Article No.: 0523014244

DOI: 10.15580/GJAS.2014.6.0523014244

Submitted: 23/05/2014

Accepted: 15/07/2014

Published: 18/07/2014

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Keywords:

cup quality, genotypes, hybrids, overall quality, screen size

ABSTRACT

Coffee grown widely in variable environments in Ethiopia has a variety of characteristics sought in the international market. Cup quality determines the relative price as well as the usefulness of a given coffee quantity. The study was conducted for three consecutive years starting from 2009/10 to 2011/12 on five hybrids and two standard checks at Awada, Wonago and Kumato. The objective of this study was to evaluate quality of Arabica Coffee under variable environment. For this study, four green bean physical characteristics (bean shape and make, color, screen size and 100 bean weight) and six cup quality traits (Aromatic intensity, aromatic quality, acidity, body, flavour and overall quality) was assessed by professional coffee tasters at Jimma Agricultural Research Center, Ethiopia. The results showed that there is a considerable variation among hybrid genotypes both for cup quality and green bean physical characteristics. Coffee samples evaluated for above screen 14 (5.60mm) revealed significant variations ($P \leq 0.001$) among hybrid coffee genotypes in all tested locations. Based on aromatic intensity, high significance difference ($P < 0.01$) was observed between hybrid coffee genotypes and strong aromatic intensity was recorded for genotypes CH₁ (3.77) and CH₅ (3.67) at Awada which was better than the two checks. Moreover, coffee genotype was showed very high significant ($P \leq 0.01$) variations with acidity at Awada, whereas significant ($P \leq 0.05$) difference was achieved at Wonago and Kumato. Based on over all cup quality, all hybrid genotypes were revealed significant ($P \leq 0.05$) variation at Awada and Kumato. Regardless of productivity and disease resistant character it can be recommended; CH₁ and CH₅ for the study area and similar coffee growing agro ecology of Sidama and Yirgacheffe, Southern Ethiopia.

INTRODUCTION

Ethiopia is the single known center of origin and genetic diversity for Arabica coffee (*Coffea arabica* L.) (Wintegens, 2004). The endowment of Ethiopia with diverse coffee types and agro-ecology allowed production of high quality coffee to world market. Coffee grow widely in variable environments in Ethiopia has a variety of characteristics sought in the international market.

The quality of coffee can be defined as its organoleptic cup-quality, physical appearances and inherent chemical constituents of a green bean produced. Coffee quality is of critical importance to the coffee industry. Production and supply of coffee with excellent quality appear more crucial than ever before for coffee exporting countries. Quality coffee is a product that has desirable characteristics such as clean raw and roasted appearance, attractive aroma and good cup taste (Behailu et al., 2008). Coffee quality encompasses beans flavor in fragrance, aroma, flavor, sweetness, acidity or overall taste felt by consumer after drink as well as physical characteristics such as length, width, thickness or weights, shape and color of coffee beans (Giomo et al., 2012).

The quality of coffee is strongly influenced by environmental factor (Decasy et al., 2003). Altitude, daily temperature fluctuations, amount and distribution of rainfall and the physical and chemical characteristics of the soil are very important factors. The production of good quality coffee beans in specific areas characterized by their climatic conditions, clearly showed that climate is one of the important factor in determining quality of coffee beverage (Silva et al., 2005). According to Leroy et al. (2006), genetic origins greatly influenced coffee quality. Coffee quality is also depends up on the genetic make-up genotype/variety and the environmental conditions in which grown, this favors genes of chemical compounds that behave as aroma precursors expressed during coffee roasting process (Yigzaw, 2005).

In Ethiopia, especially the southern region is the second largest producer and supplier of Arabica coffee. Sidama and Gedeo represent the major coffee growing zones in the southern region where different *Coffea arabica* landraces are known to exist (Taye et al., 2004). These coffee types have their own distinct growth characters and quality used to distinguish them. The existence of vast genetic variability in *Coffea arabica* genotypes of Ethiopia creates the opportunity for improvement through selection and hybridization with

good yield performance, resistance to major diseases with distinct quality characters. Currently, 37 improved (34 varieties and-3 hybrids) coffee varieties and released coffee berry disease resistant varieties (Abrar and Negussie, 2013). The three hybrids are suitable and released for the southwest part of the country.

Still now there is no hybrid developed and released for South region. Selections and hybrids should be tested for their raw and cup quality. The existence of vast genetic variability in *Coffea arabica* genotypes of Ethiopia creates the opportunity for improvement through selection and hybridization with good yield performance, resistance to major diseases with distinct quality characters. The development of local landraces for each locality largely based on their like coffee berry disease and quality would help to reduce quality adulteration of the inherent quality of known coffees in the country. The objective of this study was to evaluate Arabica coffee hybrids for their performance across different environment for raw and cup quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the study areas

The experiment was conducted at Awada Agricultural Research Sub Center, and Wonago and Kumato trial sites located in southern Ethiopia. Awada is located at an altitude of 1750 meters above sea level and also Wonago (1850masl), Kumato (1600 masl). Awada and Kumato are in Sidama zone where as Wonago is located in Gedeo zone. Samples were prepared at Awada and Wonago. The quality attributes analysis was made at Jimma Agricultural Research Center by a team (Three cuppers) of experienced and internationally certified Q grader professional panelists.

Experimental material and design: The study was carried out for three consecutive years starting from 2009/10 to 2011/12 on five hybrids and two standard checks (Ababuna and Angafa). The experiment was superimposed on hybrids coffee verification experimental plots with three replications at each location. The experimental fields were laid out 15 trees per plot planted in 2x2m spacing. All the management practices such as shading, weeding and fertilization were uniformly applied to all plots as per the recommendation.

Table 1: List of coffee genotype used for experiment

Ser no.	Coffee genotype	Character
1	744x1377 (HC₁)	Hybrid
2	7440x2077 (HC₂)	Hybrid
3	75227x1377 (HC₃)	Hybrid
4	75227x2077 (HC₄)	Hybrid
5	75227x1681(HC₅)	Hybrid
6	Ababuna (C₁)	Released (Cheek Hybrid)
7	Angafa (C₂)	Released (Cheek Pure line)

Experimental procedure: About six kg red ripe coffee cherries were handpicked from all replication and bulked for each coffee type. Prior to pulping over mature, green cherries and foreign material were sorted out from healthy and red ripe cherries. The samples were carefully prepared using wet processing method (pulping, fermentation, and drying) and prepared for sensorial analysis using the following procedures.

Sample preparation: Fully ripened red coffee samples were pulped using single disc manual pulper beans from the skin and pulp. The wet parchment coffee was left to fermentation for 40 hour till first washing made. Then, samples were soaked for 24 h before the final washing. The samples were placed on raised mesh wire under sun for drying. During drying, the moisture content of the parchment coffee was measured by moisture tester H-E50 to maintain the moisture level at 10.5-11.0% for all samples uniformly. After the samples had the recommended moisture content collected and hulled to attain clean washed coffee. Each sample was sub divided into three for replication. About 300 g of green coffee bean samples were prepared per replication separately for each genotypes for raw and cup quality characteristics evaluation.

Raw quality analysis: During raw quality analysis, 300g of green bean was used for each sample and their above screen size 14(%), 100 bean weight (gm), shape, make and color were measured as follows. Screen size carried out by means of rounded perforated plate called screen. The screen size holes was 14 (1/64 inch of 14) which means 5.6mm coffee bean retained above recorded in percentage. Shape and make was evaluated as very good, good, fairly good, average, and small and weighted accordingly using ranges 1 to 5 scale. Color was evaluated as bluish, Grayish, greenish, coated and faded using ranges 1 to 5 scale. 100 beans weight for each sample was measured in gram using sensitive weight scale.

Roasting and grinding: The roaster machine, probatBRZ6, was first heated at about 200°C. About 100 g of green coffee bean sample prepared per replication was used for roasting. Coffee samples were roasted medium roast (eight minute on average); it was tipped out into the cooling try. Cold air was blown through the coffee to produce rapid cooling-off. When the roast was

cool, it was blown to remove the loose silver skins before grinding. Each sample was grinded to medium seized ground using Mahlkoing electrical grinder.

Brewing: Soon after grinding, coffee powder weighing about 8g was placed in a cup with a capacity of 180 mL. Then, boiling water was poured on to the ground coffee up to about half way in the cup. Soon after, volatile aromatic quality and intensity parameters were recorded by sniffing. Then, the contents of the cup were stirred to ensure an infusion of all coffee grounds. The cup was then filled to the brim with boiled (about 92°C) water. The brew was made ready for panelists within 8 min.

Cup quality analysis: it was carried out once the beverage cooled to around 60°C (drinkable temperature). Three cups per sample were prepared for tasting session. The coffee type and the replicates were arranged at random. The cup quality attributes Aromatic Quality, Aromatic Intensity, Acidity, Body, Flavor and Overall Cup Quality were scored using scales ranging from 0 to 5. Each panelist gave his/her independent judgment for each sample unit of the treatment. Finally, the average results of all panelists were used for data analysis.

Data analysis: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was computed for each quality parameter in order to identify the variability among the coffee type based on the procedures described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). SAS statistical software Version 9.2 (SAS, 2008) was employed for ANOVA, in CRD with three replications. For characters having significant mean differences, the difference between treatment means was compared using LSD at 5% probability level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bean sizes: Coffee samples evaluated for above screen 14 (5.60mm) revealed significant variations ($P \leq 0.001$) among coffee types from Awada, Wonago and Kumato. Accordingly, the highest bold and large bean size was recorded in CH₁ and-CH₅ in which 99.13 % of the beans retained above screen 14 at Awada. On the other hand, CH₂-had the smallest bean size with 96.93% of the beans retained above the screen (Table-2). The highest bold and large bean size was recorded from HC₅ and C₂

in which was 98.17% of the beans retained above the screen from Wonago site. 95.13% of the beans retained above screen was achieved for HC₄ (Table 3). Genotype CH₅ and C₂ were the boldest and largest bean size, in which 97.27% of the beans retained above the screen achieved at Kumato research site. On the contrary, CH₄ had 94.43% bean was retained above screen (Table 4). Bean size is determined by screening that has a particular importance to roasters since bean size would be exposed to roast uniformly, which is influenced by botanical variety and growth environment (Yigzaw, 2005; EAFCA, 2008).

Shape and Make: There was significant ($P \leq 0.01$) variation in the shape and make of coffee genotypes planted at Awada. The highest figure was recorded for CH₁, CH₃ and CH₅ with an average value of 4.43, which is a very good shape and make with more uniform appearance (Table 2) similar with C₂. The lowest (3.87) was recorded from genotypes CH₂, indicating its smallest bean size for Awada site. Coffee genotypes depicted significant ($P \leq 0.001$) variation for the shape and make evaluated at Wonago with the highest (4.33) and lowest (3.5) average values obtained for CH₅ and CH₃ respectively (Table 3). At Kumato site highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) difference between coffee types was achieved for shape and make raw quality. Good shape and make (3.93) was recorded for CH₅ and the lowest (3.17) was for CH₃. Bean physical characteristics such as bean size, shape and make are unified criteria for conducting coffee business within the international market (Agwanda *et al.*, 2003). Uniform, bold and heavy coffee beans are the most preferred and are usually priced high. Identification of gene sources for desirable green bean physical characteristics is crucial for the development of coffee varieties with desirable green bean physical characteristics.

Color: The results showed significant ($P \leq 0.001$) differences among genotype at Awada and Wonago study sites. Thus, for the Awada coffee the highest result with the grayish to bluish color were found for genotypes CH₅ and C₁ whereas the least coated greenish to grayish was recorded for CH₁ and CH₄ genotype (Table 2). At Wonago the highest value (3.93) grayish color was recorded for CH₂ and CH₅, least value (3.20) was found for C₂. Significant ($P \leq 0.05$) differences among genotypes evaluated at Kumato were achieved. Genotype CH₅ and C₂ had got higher value (3.67) and lower value (3.17) of color quality respectively (Table 4). The quality attribute color showed difference across the three study sites, this may be due to environmental effect on coffee types. Coffee beans with the poorest appearance can be observed due to coffee type and processing methods (Sutherland, 1990). The best green blue coffee bean color can be obtained by removing the mucilage under fermentation after removing the pulp in wet processing (Anon, 2001).

Bean Weight: Coffee genotypes harvested from Awada, Wonago and Kumato were highly influenced ($P \leq 0.001$) by coffee genotype for 100-bean weight (Table 2). Genotype CH₁ was found to be the heaviest (20.17gm) when compared with all the other coffee genotypes grown under Awada agro climatic conditions. HC₂ was found the lightest (15.87) 100 bean weight than the other coffee evaluated at Awada (Table 2). At Wonago among the genotypes, CH₁ had the heaviest beans with a mean 100 bean weight of 18.60g while C₁ was the lightest with mean bean weight of 13.27g (Table 3). Under Kumato condition the heaviest bean weight was recorded for CH₁ with a mean value of 17.53g. On the other hand, C₁ had light bean weight of 13.10 g (Table 4). The result, therefore, indicates the existing heterogeneity among coffee genotypes for bean weight characteristics. This corroborates with other authors who reported that Arabica coffee were diverse in average bean weight (Wintegens, 2004; Yigzaw, 2005).

Aromatic Intensity: Aromatic intensity was significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced by coffee genotype. Strong aromatic intensity was recorded for CH₁ (3.77) similar with CH₅ (3.67) at Awada which was better than the two cheeks. On the other hand the lower aromatic intensity was achieved for CH₄ (3.20). At Wonago, the aromatic intensity was highly influenced ($P \leq 0.05$) due to genetic variation. CH₁ achieved strong aromatic intensity (3.67). Among other treatments there were no significant differences. At Kumato there was no significant difference among all coffee genotype for aromatic intensity. Van der Vossen (2005) also reported mean performance variation for cup quality character indicating the presence of great variability among Arabica coffee genotypes.

Aromatic Quality: Aromatic quality was significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by genotype at Awada and Wonago. Good aromatic quality (3.60) was recorded for CH₁ and the lowest value was (3.27) observed for C₁. Similar result was achieved at Wonago which was significantly ($P < 0.01$) affected by genotype. CH₁ had got better aromatic quality (3.50) and the lowest quality (3.07) was achieved for CH₃. Aromatic quality was not affected by coffee type at Kumato. The result indicates the variability cup quality attributes among Arabica coffee genotypes.

Acidity: Coffee genotypes showed significant ($P \leq 0.01$) variations with acidity at Awada, whereas significant ($P \leq 0.05$) difference achieved at Wonago and Kumato. Consequently, at Awada the highest moderately pointed mean value (3.60) acidity was recorded for CH₁, while the least medium mean value (3.00) acidity recorded for C₁ (Table 2). Similarly CH₁ and CH₄ showed the highest medium pointed mean value (3.40) acidity and the least medium (2.83) acidity respectively at Wonago (Table 3). At Kumato, CH₅ had the highest medium pointed (3.50) acidity and the least medium (2.87) acidity were recorded for CH₃ (Table 4). A variation in acidity among coffee genotypes collected from the different parts of

Ethiopia was reported by Yigzaw (2005). According to Agwanda (1999), acidity and body are reliable and suitable quality attribute that can be used as selection criteria for the genetic improvement of coffee quality.

Body: Body assesses the beverage mouth feel or the property linked with density and viscosity of the brew. There was significant ($P \leq 0.05$) variation of coffee type on the body in the case of Awada and Kumato. Coffee genotype CH₃ had the highest medium full (3.53) while CH₃ and CH₄ showed the medium body (Table 2). At Wonago, the coffee type had highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$) variation in body. CH₁ had medium full body while C₂ had least medium (3.03) body (Table 3). Coffee type C₂ had medium full body (3.60) similar with CH₁, CH₂, CH₃, and CH₄ while minimum value (3.30) was recorded for CH₅, and C₁ at Kumato (Table 4). The result agreed with Agwanda (1999) in acidity and body for their suitability as a selection criterion for the genetic improvement of coffee quality and there was variation in their body among genotypes of *Coffea arabica* (Yigzaw, 2005).

Flavour: Flavour indicates fragrance of the liquor either by direct inhaling of the vapours arising from the cup or nasal perception of the volatile substances evolving in the mouth. Significant ($P \leq 0.05$) coffee genotype variations in flavour were achieved at Awada and Wonago. Out of the 7 coffee types evaluated three were average to good flavour, CH₁ had got average to good flavour value (3.53) and while C₁ was fair to average (2.97) flavour value recorded at Awada. At Wonago, CH₁ had average to good flavour value (3.27) while CH₃ and CH₄ had fair to average (2.50) flavour (Table 3). Coffee genotype significant ($P \leq 0.01$) variation in flavour was achieved in the case of Kumato research site. As a result genotype C₂ had medium full body (3.60) similar with CH₁, CH₂, CH₃, and CH₄ while minimum value (3.30) was recorded for CH₅, and C₁ (Table 4). Walyaro (1983) showed the presence of large inherent difference among genotypes for cup quality attributes. Van der Vossen (2005) also observed variation for cup quality character among varieties and crosses of Arabica coffee.

Overall cup quality: The evaluated coffee genotype showed significant ($P \leq 0.05$) variation for overall cup quality at Awada and Kumato. CH₁ had got good to very good overall cup quality value (3.40) similar with CH₂

and CH₅, while 3.06 overall cup quality values was recorded for CH₃ at Awada (Table 2). Highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$) genotype variation in overall cup quality was achieved at Wonago. Genotype CH₁ and CH₂ had an average value of 3.20 and 3.17 overall cup quality respectively (Table 3). In addition the lowest value of 2.47 overall cup quality obtained from genotype CH₃. High mean overall cup quality value (3.37) was recorded from genotype CH₅ as opposed to the relatively lower values (2.80) recorded from genotypes CH₁ at Kumato (Table 4). The significant variations among coffee hybrids for quality traits indicated that the existence of variability due to an effective hybridization for improvements. The result showed there is presence of large inherent difference among genotypes for overall cup quality attributes. Variation for overall cup quality character among genotype of Arabica coffee is good opportunity for selection and hybridization. Van der Vossen (2005) also reported mean performance variation for cup quality character among varieties and crosses of *Coffea arabica* L, indicating the presence of great variability among Arabica coffee genotypes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the overall quality attribute result used to determine and evaluate the potential of the hybrid coffee genotypes. Considerable variation was observed among genotypes both for cup quality and green bean physical characteristics. Therefore there is an opportunity to select genotypes with desirable raw and cup quality characteristics. Based on the quality parameters CH₁ and CH₅ showed very good row and cup test results in the study areas. So, these hybrid coffee types can be recommended for production if their yielding ability and disease resistance is reasonably good for the study area and similar coffee growing agro ecology of Sidama and Yigracheffe in Southern Ethiopia.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledged the certified professional cuppers of Jimma Agricultural Research Centre. We also extend our sincere thanks to the coffee breeder and the supporting staff for assisting in coffee sample preparation.

Table 2: Raw and cup quality attributes of coffee genotypes evaluated at Awada

Coffee Type	Raw Quality					Cup Quality				
	% Sc.14	SM	Color	HBW (gm)	AI	AQ	AC	BO	FL	OAQ
CH ₁	99.13 ^a	4.43 ^a	4.00 ^c	20.17 ^a	3.77 ^a	3.60 ^a	3.53 ^a	3.53 ^a	3.53 ^a	3.40 ^a
CH ₂	96.93 ^d	3.87 ^c	4.33 ^b	15.87 ^f	3.50 ^{bc}	3.50 ^{ab}	3.40 ^{ab}	3.37 ^{ab}	3.33 ^{ab}	3.30 ^{ab}
CH ₃	98.10 ^b	4.27 ^{ab}	4.33 ^b	17.33 ^d	3.43 ^c	3.43 ^{ab}	3.07 ^{cd}	3.17 ^b	3.07 ^{bc}	3.06 ^c
CH ₄	98.10 ^b	4.10 ^{bc}	4.00 ^c	17.73 ^c	3.20 ^d	3.53 ^a	3.10 ^{cd}	3.10 ^b	3.10 ^{bc}	3.10 ^{bc}
CH ₅	99.03 ^a	4.43 ^a	4.67 ^a	18.87 ^b	3.67 ^{ab}	3.50 ^{ab}	3.30 ^{abc}	3.33 ^{ab}	3.23 ^{abc}	3.23 ^{abc}
C ₁	97.17 ^{cd}	4.10 ^{bc}	4.67 ^a	16.27 ^e	3.53 ^{bc}	3.27 ^b	3.00 ^d	3.27 ^{ab}	2.97 ^c	3.10 ^{bc}
C ₂	97.23 ^c	4.30 ^{ab}	4.50 ^{ab}	17.37 ^d	3.55 ^{bc}	3.40 ^{ab}	3.20 ^{bcd}	3.30 ^{ab}	3.07 ^{bc}	3.17 ^{bc}
CV%	0.16	3.76	4.09	0.73	3.26	3.83	4.10	5.26	6.09	4.03
LSD(5%)	0.28	0.28	0.32	0.23	0.20	0.24	0.24	0.31	0.35	0.23

* Mean values with similar letter(s) in the column are not significantly different at P<0.05

** Sc.14% = percent of above screen 14, SM = Shape and make, Co = Color, AI = Aromatic Quality, AQ = Aromatic Intensity, AC = Acidity, BO = Body, FL = Flavor and OAQ = Overall Quality

Table 3: Raw and cup quality attributes of coffee genotypes evaluated at Wonago

Coffee Type	Raw Quality					Cup Quality				
	Sc.14%	SM	Color	Bwt (gm)	AI	AQ	AC	BO	FL	OAQ
CH ₁	97.10 ^b	4.00 ^{ab}	3.67 ^b	18.60 ^a	3.67 ^a	3.50 ^a	3.40 ^a	3.53 ^a	3.27 ^a	3.20 ^a
CH ₂	96.13 ^c	3.67 ^{bc}	3.93 ^a	14.43 ^e	3.30 ^b	3.27 ^{ab}	2.97 ^{bc}	3.37 ^{ab}	2.70 ^{abc}	3.17 ^a
CH ₃	97.10 ^b	3.50 ^c	3.63 ^b	16.20 ^c	3.37 ^{ab}	3.07 ^b	3.03 ^{abc}	3.13 ^{cd}	2.50 ^c	2.47 ^c
CH ₄	95.13 ^d	3.42 ^c	3.90 ^a	14.27 ^e	3.30 ^b	3.17 ^b	2.83 ^c	3.20 ^{bcd}	2.53 ^c	2.60 ^{bc}
CH ₅	98.17 ^a	4.33 ^a	3.93 ^a	17.27 ^b	3.30 ^b	3.20 ^b	3.27 ^{ab}	3.23 ^{bc}	3.17 ^{ab}	2.97 ^{ab}
C ₁	91.10 ^e	3.67 ^{bc}	3.90 ^a	13.27 ^f	3.33 ^b	3.27 ^{ab}	3.37 ^{ab}	3.10 ^{cd}	3.00 ^{abc}	2.93 ^{ab}
C ₂	98.17 ^a	3.60 ^c	3.20 ^c	15.13 ^d	3.40 ^b	3.13 ^b	3.27 ^{ab}	3.03 ^d	2.80 ^{abc}	3.00 ^a
CV%	0.11	5.25	3.45	0.91	5.14	4.21	7.60	3.33	10.86	7.44
LSD (5%)	0.19	0.35	0.23	0.25	0.31	0.24	0.43	0.19	0.59	0.38

* Mean values with similar letter(s) in the column are not significantly different at P<0.05

** Sc.14% = percent of above screen 14, SM = Shape and make, Co = Color, AI = Aromatic Quality, AQ = Aromatic Intensity, AC = Acidity, BO = Body, FL = Flavor and OAQ = Overall Quality

Table 4: Raw and cup quality attributes of coffee genotypes evaluated at Kumato

Coffee Type	Raw Quality					Cup Quality				
	Sc.14%	SM	Color	Bwt (gm)	AI	AQ	AC	BO	FL	OAQ
CH ₁	96.03 ^b	3.50 ^b	3.50 ^a	17.53 ^a	3.45	2.98	3.00 ^{bc}	3.37 ^{ab}	2.70 ^d	2.80 ^b
CH ₂	95.17 ^c	3.33 ^{bc}	3.43 ^{ab}	13.53 ^e	3.37	3.47	3.40 ^{ab}	3.53 ^{ab}	3.27 ^{ab}	3.20 ^{ab}
CH ₃	96.20 ^c	3.17 ^c	3.40 ^{ab}	15.40 ^c	3.51	3.18	2.87 ^c	3.37 ^{ab}	2.87 ^{cd}	2.90 ^b
CH ₄	94.43 ^d	3.27 ^{bc}	3.57 ^a	13.23 ^f	3.57	3.34	3.27 ^{abc}	3.37 ^{ab}	3.13 ^{abc}	3.13 ^{ab}
CH ₅	97.30 ^a	3.93 ^a	3.67 ^a	16.17 ^b	3.48	3.30	3.50 ^a	3.30 ^b	3.47 ^a	3.37 ^a
C ₁	91.10 ^e	3.33 ^{bc}	3.53 ^a	13.10 ^f	3.39	3.18	3.00 ^{bc}	3.30 ^b	2.93 ^{bcd}	2.93 ^b
C ₂	97.27 ^a	3.43 ^{bc}	3.17 ^b	14.20 ^d	3.48	3.18	3.30 ^{ab}	3.60 ^a	3.06 ^{bcd}	3.03 ^{ab}
CV%	0.15	5.09	4.80	0.91	5.79	9.54	7.61	4.92	6.77	7.57
LSD(5%)	0.26	0.31	0.30	0.24	NS	NS	0.43	0.29	0.37	0.41

* Mean values with similar letter(s) in the column are not significantly different at P<0.05

** Sc.14% = percent of above screen 14, SM = Shape and make, Co = Color, AI = Aromatic Quality, AQ = Aromatic Intensity, AC = Acidity, BO = Body, FL = Flavor and OAQ = Overall Quality

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Cite this Article: Abrar S, Negussie M, Meseret D, 2014. Hybrid Coffee (*Coffea arabica* L) Genotypes Quality Evaluation under different Environment of Southern Ethiopia. Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences. 4(6):245-251. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.2014.6.0523014244>.